

Twitter's consolidated financial statements informed why and who it censored for

The image shows two screenshots from a Twitter account. The top screenshot is titled "Remove Tweet." and shows a tweet by "CPA Jim" (@TheCCPA) from October 23, 2020. The tweet text is: "In the first three quarters of 2020, 90-day above delinquency rate of non-performing loans was 80.2% in the CCP banking sector. It highlights that the economy is deteriorating, and numerous enterprise just lived by renewing debts! <https://t.co/iRzThstGL>". Below the tweet is a red "Remove" button and explanatory text about the removal process and appeal options.

The bottom screenshot is titled "Thanks for your appeal" and shows a confirmation that the user has appealed 1 tweet. The tweet being appealed is by "CPA Jim" (@TheCCPA) from October 25, 2020. The tweet text is: "@mizdouma @TDelyfer His son performed sex in Communist China paid by Chinese Communist Party. Take down the CCP. #TakeDownTheCCP <https://t.co/WTeEgxHf1o>". Below the tweet is text explaining that the account will be locked during the appeal review process and providing a link to cancel the appeal.

Picture Resource: Twitter

On 24 October 2020, an email from Twitter (TWTR) informed me that my TWTR account has been locked. Then I decided to appeal this suspension. There's a snapshot of this email as follows. The censorship logic of TWTR is similar to Weibo under the digital totalitarian of Chinese Communist Party (CCP) that is politician family's inmate photos shouldn't be published without approval of those corrupted politicians' family members.

However, on 31 October 2020 just posting economic issues followed a link to Gnews. org resulting in account being locked.

Twitter ☆
notify@twitter.com

Send email View profile

Results

Filter

Twitter	Your Twitter account has been locked	Hi CPA Jim, Your account, @TheCICPA has been lock...	Inbox	2:24
Twitter	Your account has been restored	Hello, Our support team has reviewed your account and it...	Inbox	Thu 8:54
Twitter	We've received your appeal request	Hello, We've received your appeal request. Our suppo...	Inbox	Thu 8:49
Twitter	Your Twitter account has been locked	Hi CPA Jim, Your account, @TheCICPA has been lock...	Inbox	Thu 8:42
Twitter	Your account has been restored	Hello, Our support team has reviewed your account and it...	Inbox	Wed 16:00
Twitter	We've received your appeal request	Hello, We've received your appeal request. Our suppo...	Inbox	Sun 25/10
Twitter Support	About your Twitter account 0177941793 [ref:00DA0000000K0A8.5004A0000214eA4:ref]	He...	Inbox	Sat 24/10
Twitter	Your Twitter account has been locked	Hi CPA Jim, Your account, @TheCICPA has been lock...	Inbox	Sat 24/10

Your Twitter account has been locked

Hi CPA Jim,
Your account, @TheCICPA has
been locked for violating the
[Twitter Rules](#).

Specifically for:

Violating our rules against posting or sharing
[privately produced/distributed intimate media](#) of
someone without their express consent.

Please note that repeated violations may lead to a
permanent suspension of your account. Proceed to
Twitter now to fix the issue with your account.

[Go to Twitter](#)

Then who was encouraging TWTR's censorship with fund? Who was supplying TWTR censorship with human resource?

Let's get to the financial statements of TWTR which can help you understand why investment in TWTR's shares is likely to result in huge loss and CCP is manipulating TWTR performance and share price to encourage TWTR censorship.

How did TWTR realize income leap forward?

According to consolidated financial statements as of both 31 December 2016^[1] and 31 December 2019^[2], both of which were given unqualified audit opinions by the same auditor PricewaterhouseCoopers LLP in San Francisco, California where there were many CCP's spies, comprehensive income (CI) as well as profit or loss (PL) for the years from 2014 to 2017 were suffering loss as follows followed by significant earnings from 2018 on. According to the numbers extracted from the above reports, a chart was drawn as below. It's found that from 2017 to 2018, there was a great jump similar to Great Leap Forward between 1958 and early 1960^[3].

By calculating return on sales (here, return on sales=CI÷Revenue), we can get that its financial performance jump in 2018 was due to surge of return on sales as follows as well as revenue increase.

It can be inferred from the above that in 2018 TWTR realised additional great income by performing contract obligations with abnormal profit ratio. Then what is the contract obligation of Twitter exactly as the consideration for such revenue?

Beginning of Whistleblower's Movement

As informed by Miles Guo on 5 October 2017 on the press conference held in Washington D. C, The CCP Kleptocrats had been currently implementing 3F and BGY in the US, very successfully and swiftly, which would make an enormous harm to the Americans and their lives and properties, might 100 even 1000 times worse than 9/11. BGY stands for Blue, Gold and Yellow. Blue represents Internet and Media Control. Gold represents money and bribery is used to buy influence. Yellow represents the use of honey traps to compromise espionage targets. CCP planned to control the world by choking the throats of the world leaders, politicians, media, academics and financial operators; and it had deeply invaded the US

from within via this BGY in the past decades. 3F means to foment weakness, foment chaos and foment the destruction of America.[4]

As reported by BEAST INSIDE on 16 October 2020, Bannon's cooperation with Miles Guo on Whistleblower's Movement began shortly after Bannon's leaving the White House in August 2017. By 2018, the pair began appearing regularly on its GNews website. [5] Another story told that since commencement of Miles Guo Whistleblower's Movement in 2017, TWTR has been experiencing user quantity increase in Chinese world and met more potential business opportunities brought by Miles Guo and whistle-blower movement members.[6]

Number of TWTR Monetizable DAU worldwide (in millions)

Note: Monetizable DAU are Twitter users who log in and access Twitter on any given day through Twitter.com or Twitter applications that are able to show ads.

Resource: Statista[7]

TWTR is just another traitor that sold American state security to CCP for money, besides Joe Biden.

According to personal experiences, Twitter has offered ads service to Huawei, the national security threat of USA[8], of promoting junk stuffs and misleading many Chinese and other countries' users on electronic communication equipment purchasing decisions and should have received tremendous contract consideration from Huawei. In the ads rendered to TWTR users, TWTR failed to identify Huawei as a security threat while it could identify government account and censor content.

TWTR has also promoted the accounts of foreign agents including People’s Daily and Hu Xijin. Did those contract obligations provided in those ads contracts include censoring services? Did those contracts designate a CCP member responsible for supervising censorship implementation as an independent director to TWTR for additional consideration?

Whistleblower’s Movement lead by Miles, whose aim is to take down the CCP, started in 2017 and it needed social media to spread truths of Hong Kong crises as well as other CCP plagues. The commencement date of CCP ads contract signed with TWTR may be in 2017 followed by Miles’ Twitter account being suspended. Despite Mile’s account being suspended, Whistleblower’s Movement members and influence at the Twitter platform have increased significantly. As a result, CCP may think that it’s necessary to designate an independent director to TWTR’s board of directors for supervising and advising on specific censorship issues.

李飞飞重返祖国执掌Google AI中国团队：不忘初心，中国已觉醒

量子位
已认证的官方帐号
999人赞过了这篇文章

Moreover, TWTR hired another security concern Feifei Li. As reported by National Security News on 29 May 2020, a White House petition calling on the U.S. government to investigate “Twitter’s violation of freedom of speech, and on Dr. FeiFei Li’s collaborations with the CCP, a threat to national security” was created in May 2020. Li quit Google in 2018 where leaked emails revealed that she appeared to be against Google’s work on Project Maven, a U.S. Department of Defense AI project. During her tenure at Google, Li didn’t reject controversial Project Dragonfly meant to be a search engine that would suit CCP censorship rules, as she opened an AI research facility in Beijing.^[9] In addition, Li allegedly has ties to a student association that is affiliated with the CCP’s United Front, according to Radio Free Asia.

Softbank’s insane purchase of tech stocks and their call options

According to *Proxy Statement*^[10] filed with SEC by TWTR on 15 April 2020, On the date of each annual meeting of stockholders, each of its non-employee directors is granted restricted stock units (“RSUs”) having a grant date fair value approximately equal to \$225,000, computed in accordance with Financial Accounting Standards Board (“FASB”), Accounting Standards Codification (“ASC”), Topic 718.

“The shares of our common stock underlying the RSUs vest in quarterly installments beginning on the first quarter following the date of grant (on the same day of the month as the date of grant) but will vest in full on the date of the next annual meeting of stockholders if not fully vested on such date, subject to continued service through each vesting date. Directors who are appointed mid-year receive a pro-rated RSU grant based on the number of months between their appointment date and the date of our next annual meeting of stockholders. **Directors who are appointed mid-year receive a pro-rated RSU grant** based on the number of months between their appointment date and the date of our next annual meeting of stockholders.”

It followed outlining compensation details which showed that most compensation of non-employee directors in 2019 was paid using stock compensation.

Compensation structure of non-employee directors	Row No.	Cash Compensation (\$)	Stock Compensation	Total	Ratio
Column No.	1	1	2	3=1+2	4=2÷3
Martha Lane Fox	2	70,000.00	223,164.00	293,164.00	76.12%
Debra Lee	3	27,083.00	223,164.00	250,247.00	89.18%
Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala	4	54,167.00	233,076.00	287,243.00	81.14%
Patrick Pichette	5	90,000.00	223,164.00	313,164.00	71.26%

Compensation structure of non-employee directors	Row No.	Cash Compensation (\$)	Stock Compensation	Total	Ratio
David Rosenblatt	6	82,917.00	223,164.00	306,081.00	72.91%
Bret Taylor	7	-	282,676.00	282,676.00	100.00%
Evan Williams	8	45,833.00	-	45,833.00	0.00%
Robert Zoellick	9	53,333.00	223,164.00	276,497.00	80.71%
Total	10=2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9	423,333.00	1,631,572.00	2,054,905.00	79.40%

Therefore, directors were impacted significantly by stocks’ market value where nearly average 80% of non-employee directors’ compensation was stock compensation. 92% of 2019 compensation for its Named Executive Officers on average as a group (excluding CEO who declined all compensation other than a base salary of \$1.40) was attributable to equity compensation.

As of 31 December 2019, all executive officers and directors as a group (14 persons) owned 20,741,693 TWTR shares. Besides, the Employee Stock Purchase Plan indicated that Equity compensation plans approved by security holders provided 36,266,939 shares to be issued to employees at weighted average exercise price \$10.27 upon exercise of outstanding options, warrants and rights. Other censorship techs and BGY tools including Facebook, Google, Wall Street bankers have similar compensation arrangement.

As pointed out by ZeroHedge (ZH) in the article “Connecting The Dots: How SoftBank Made Billions Using The Biggest ‘Gamma Squeeze’ In History” on 7 September 2020, it was SoftBank that was using a "positive gamma" strategy of buying up single name stocks, which it then propelled higher by buying call options in the same stock. ZH in early August 2020 reported for the first time SoftBank

was targeting investments of over \$10 billion in public stocks as part of a new asset management arm, far exceeding the initial holdings that founder Masayoshi Son outlined to shareholders in the company's latest earnings call, and a break from the company's strategy of investing in private names because on 11 Aug 2020, Masa Son said SoftBank had acquired major holdings in not only the FAAMG (i.e. Facebook, Amazon, Apple, Microsoft, and Alphabet's Google) stocks but some of the highest beta, "story" tech names. It is indicated that TWTR's capitalization value is also inflated by rise of similar Tech stocks FAAMG driven by Wall Street, SoftBank and its retail clients which are influenced by CCP's BGY plan. According to email evidence exposed by Lude Media, Wall Street Journal is also controlled by CCP. CCP may make use of WSJ in spreading disinformation to manipulate techs' stock prices just as it had done for promoting Ant Group IPO by applying overstated CNY/USD exchange rate to mislead capital markets on Ant's financial performance.[\[11\]](#)

Resource: Yahoo Finance

This stock inflation directly increased TWTR management's compensation arising from stock compensation (a way for companies to pay employees in shares of stock or stock options. Stock options are the most common type of stock compensation and allow an employee to purchase the company's stock at a set price during a set vesting period[\[12\]](#)).

According to the censorship logic of TWTR as well as Facebook and Google, it's easily to conclude that besides CCP ads contract, it's also CCP that is manipulating techs' stock prices via SoftBank and Wall Street to compensate censorship obligations included in their devil business contracts. If Americans and other countries' citizens are to avoid being enslaved and take down the Great Firewall being constructed by main media, Wall Street as well as FAAMG, we are obliged to work together to take down the CCP.

- [1] 2016 Annual Report https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/1418091/000156459017002584/twtr-10k_20161231.htm
- [2] 2019 Annual Report <https://www.sec.gov/ix?doc=/Archives/edgar/data/1418091/000141809120000037/twtr-20191231.htm>
- [3] Great Leap Forward <https://www.britannica.com/event/Great-Leap-Forward>
- [4] BGY and 3F <https://gnews.org/154724/>
- [5] Whistleblower's Movement <https://www.thedailybeast.com/chinese-billionaires-network-hyped-hunter-biden-dirt-weeks-before-rudy?ref=scroll>
- [6] The correlation between whistleblower Movement and Twitter usage. <https://gnews.org/zh-hans/457288/>
- [7] Twitter users (mDAU) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/970920/monetizable-daily-active-twitter-users-worldwide/>
- [8] National Security Threat <https://tech.co/news/huawei-safe-china-state-military-2020-01#:~:text=At%20the%20start%20of%202018%2C%20Verizon%20and%20AT%26T,US%20intelligence%20agencies%20advised%20against%20using%20Huawei%20devices.>
- [9] Feifei Li is national security threat. <https://nationalsecurity.news/2020-05-29-petition-calls-for-investigation-into-twitter-censorship-after-hiring-li-fei-fei.html>
- [10] Proxy Statement <https://sec.report/Document/0001140361-20-008934/>
- [11] WSJ mislead Ant Group's financial performance. <https://cpajim.blogspot.com/2020/09/main-media-mislead-public-on-ccp.html>
- [12] Stock compensation <https://www.wikihow.com/Account-for-Stock-Based-Compensation>